

TATTOOS AND THEIR MEANINGS: WHAT DO THEY REVEAL ABOUT THE PERSONOLOGICAL STATE OF THE INDIVIDUAL?

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ABSTRACT

This essay-article addresses a complex theme in the sense of providing clarifications on tattoos and their meanings, showing what they reveal about the personological state of the individual. This is a subject that defies the simple logic of the law to apply an art on the body, keeping an entire historical scope that crosses the history of humanity, in its various dimensions. To produce this text, the authors used knowledge of semiotics, anthropology, depth psychology, semantics and religion. There is confusion about the term tattoo that was treated in the text, clarifying each terminological dimension used. When referring to tattooing, there are three elements that overlap with the term, namely: the art (the technique itself); the drawing (the symbol expressed in itself) and the draftsman (the designer, the tattoo artist in itself). In many texts it is difficult to define which of the three the author is referring to, since he does not distinguish one from the other, bringing them all mixed up as if it were something that is aggregated and that separation is impossible. The tattoo is a meaning; it expresses something that is hidden in the individual's unconscious psychological state. In order to illustrate this article, 2 case studies will be presented, in which individual tattoo users used them as literal expressions of their deepest feelings; one, in relation to a lost love and the other, in relation to his particular way of looking at life and his human existence, in the world he chose for himself. The use of tattoos (drawings) on part of the body is a technique that possibly originated from religious beliefs and superstitions and, little by little, took on spaces of marginalization, as religion and its set of miraculous protections were losing their magical effect on individuals. What is sought to be highlighted in this essay-article is that each drawing, in particular, has a unique semantic structure and the way it is expressed in the body is what will determine its symbology, portraying the conflict and its dimension in individual thought.

Keywords: Tattoo; Individual personological state; Semiotics; Semantics.

INTRODUCTION

The habit of tattooing parts of the body with different designs and images is an archaic human custom that has undergone changes in its senses of being, being seen as fashion, *status*, power, a mark of belonging to certain groups, gangs, tribes. What is not always revealed is the

latent meaning of the tattoos, and what their owners clarify is that it is their own choice, autonomous, aware of what they want to express and even claim that they researched the meaning of the images and what they represent. in diverse cultures.

Make it clear that, in nature, there are two elements that go beyond mere existential symbology: the *signifier* and the *signified*. The first meets a taxonomic precept defining, by virtue of semantics, what is considered and accepted by all as a social element, while the second gives a specific meaning to each object, linking it to the context of sociological interpretation.

When specific reference is made to the human being, each and every symbolic interpretation has a *sui generis value*, because even inserted in a society, being prone to be formed and educated in a culture that expresses its most intrinsic values, the individual experiences [and even even the collective ones] leave indelible marks that are expressed in an intriguing way, not being able to be synthesized according to the generic customs and axioms.

For traditional Japanese cultures, the design portrayed on the skin had to have a connection with the individual, something as if the two had to be in spiritual harmony. Thus, when someone wanted to paint their body, a whole ritual was performed.

When a warrior defeated a very powerful opponent, it was customary for him to consume his heart, because in this way he believed that he internalized all his vital force. Over time, this custom evolved into another form and its skin began to be used as a mechanism to demonstrate to enemies that it was taken by the spiritual and physical strength of the defeated animal and that this, when alive, caused terror in all.

A next step was to leave the image of the defeated totem animal marked on the body, as if, by engraving its figure on the skin, it internalized the creature and everything it represents. Thus, her spirit would be taken over and dominated by the beast engraved on her body, expressing, in a symbolic way, everything she represents in wild and untamed nature.

With the weakening of the power of religion, the most indomitable warriors began to engrave on their bodies the figure of animals that, through human tradition, represented power and imposed fear, each one of them represented according to the culture in which they were inserted. This is how we have the first approximation with the current custom of reproducing images of all kinds of creatures [*wild, bizarre, monstrous, elegant*] in places exposed or not by the body, with the difference that, in Antiquity, the individual knew well why he was making such and such a drawing, its real meaning and what he expected with it attached to his state of mind.

Nowadays, the practice of tattooing the body has become fashionable. For a long time it was considered a social *taboo* , with serious discrimination, failures in exams to enter various

state corporations and even private companies. Customs have changed and, with this, society has been loosening its axioms on the subject and, with the reduction of stigma, many individuals have been embroidering their bodies with a wide range of designs, from animals, flowers, weather situations, phrases, aphorisms, proverbs and other things that each one considers relevant to himself to the point of leaving engraved on his body.

What the overwhelming majority doesn't know [*and, if they do, they pretend not to or simply don't care*] is that the tattoo is a meaning; it expresses something that is hidden in the individual's unconscious psychological state. When someone asks: What is the meaning of this design tattooed on your body?

The semantic meaning of any image drawn by an artist [*animal, plant or human, word*] interpreted by semiotics has a generic value, of knowledge and broad domain, without a particular meaning. The situation changes radically when someone chooses any image for himself and merges it with his being. The meaning that it comes to express is completely particular and its understanding needs unique studies, in which the analysis goes from the generic aspect, passing through the in-depth interpretations carried out by specific techniques such as Psychoanalysis and Psychiatry, until reaching the study of personality. of the individual, in order to find the closest connection that exists between him and his tattoo.

This already clarifies that the choice for a certain image for the making of a tattoo is not conscious. The phenomenological emotional state and your personological structure of individual character are the determinants for your decision. Thus, the image that is seen expressed is a signifier and its meaning, a phenomenon to be interpreted, if not, deciphered. However, this cannot be exposed, because if so done, it would reveal what the individual is and not what he wants to look like, in a random way.

In addition, the interpretation of the expressed body painting requires many hours of intense observation, which would displease the individual with it and, it is still necessary to know about his previous life history, what he did and what he stopped doing, the reasons he led him to this, such as traumas, disappointments, losses, defeats, conquests, abandonment.

This already reveals that a tattoo hides a whole story, not always pleasant for the tattooed person. So why did you make a point of exposing it? One of the reasons is that no one [*or almost no one*] will be able to interpret its psychological meaning. In the sequence, he is obeying a primitive principle of linking to the totemic animal that he believes he represents, because incorporated in himself.

Here it is necessary to present a link between the represented animal and its condition of behavioral expression and, many times, it is the existential battles that lead to the formation

of a paradoxical state, and this link is an unconscious representation. When confronted about what, in fact, they are representing and/or revealing about themselves, they tend to deny their character described by the interpretive and descriptive analysis based on the image.

Here is the question: And when does the existential crisis that motivated the production of art about the body come to an end? Simple: replace the animal represented by another and, once again, the way this work is carried out reveals even more about the personality and character of the individual. The alteration is made using an indigo that represents the state of mind that prevails at the moment and, if the old design is completely covered, it indicates that the change was radical. However, if the new image leaves open and showing traces of the old one, this means that there was, at most, a superficial change of thought, appropriate to the moment. In its intimate state, it remains the same as before. His previous Ego is only in a state of quiescence ¹⁴and a new Ego assumes existential cathexial autonomy, that is, he presents himself to the world as he wishes to be seen; a mask used as a disguise to cover up another mask (NIETZSCHE, 2006).

TATTOOS

When referring to tattooing, there are three elements that overlap with the term, namely: the art (the technique itself); the drawing (the symbol expressed in itself) and the draftsman (the *designer, the tattoo artist* in itself). In many texts it is difficult to define which of the three the author is referring to, since he does not distinguish one from the other, bringing them all mixed up as if it were something that is aggregated and that separation is impossible.

What matters in this text is to deal with the symbol chosen by the individual to be applied on his body, by a *designer*, using a technique. The expertise of this professional is *a sine qua non condition* for determining the final aesthetics of the design; however, it does not change its meaning at all, for the simple fact that no one arrives at a tattoo parlor and tells the designer to make any design on their skin, in a certain region. He is offered a sample of varied images, from which he will choose the one that most attracts him, without knowing the real reasons that led him to that. It is interesting that, the more beautiful a tattoo is, in terms of colors, hues, contrasts, brightness and enhancement, the lesser the social resistance to appreciating it and the

¹⁴ *Quiescence* : In Biology, refers to a physiological state of low metabolic activity characterized by low water content in tissues. Dehydration is necessary to maintain low metabolism and thus tissue viability for long periods until environmental conditions favor germination. It is a state of dormancy. In Psychoanalysis, it refers to a psychological state of latency, in which a certain state of thought or libido is not manifest. This condition can produce an illusion, providing false judgments about the studied object. (The authors, 2022)

greater the [even individual] resistance to judging it with moral *value* . derogatory cause. This is where the search for an experienced tattoo artist comes into play, with work recognized in the market for its aesthetic exuberance, a curious fact, because the professional's expertise does not make a bizarre design stop being bizarre; it makes all the elements and colors position themselves so connected and in such a synchronous way that this makes the human brain feel excited to such an extent that it is forced to praise the work of art (the tattoo).

Regarding the origin of the word tattoo, it derives from the French *tatouage* and, in turn, from the English *tattoo* , having its origin in Polynesian languages (Tahitian), derived from the word *tatau*, which was a type of sound produced during the making of the piece , and it is supposed that all the peoples surrounding the Pacific Ocean had the tradition of tattooing. Possibly, this is because primitive people were, for the most part, fierce warriors and paintings helped to produce a certain type of power and intimidation against enemies, especially those who were superstitious.

Gabriel Gonçalves reports that,

Tattooing is a process that consists of inserting ink into the skin, from a needle that penetrates the epidermis, introducing the pigment in order to definitively mark the person with the chosen design. The themes of the tattoos are endless, artistically representing everything the tattoo artist sees and feels in his day to day life. From the techniques of realism that allow the perfect representation of the art created on the skin, to the elaboration of more obscure themes, abusing black ink, tattooing has become an increasingly common and successful practice, bringing works of art to the appreciation of art lovers. increasingly detailed and vibrant, strengthening the artistic character still lacking affirmation in society (GONÇALVES, 2017, p. 9).

One thing that draws attention in this author's speech is that, in his exposition, he emphasizes all the subjective expression of the drawing to the *designer's particular feeling* . If that were the case, there would be no *pathological link* between the individual and the art written on his body. It is always necessary to clarify that the role of the tattoo artist is that of a technician, limiting himself to this, because the occasion of the intimate choice of what he will apply on his skin, be it an animal, a plant, a verse or a flower cannot be shared with anyone, even if you ask anyone for help. A whole set of deep, incomprehensible and obscure feelings, resulting from individual experiences traversed throughout existence, are what determine the form and caricature of the definitive piece, especially with regard to colors. These express the feelings that each individual maintains, in supposed secrecy, in their intrinsic world and, in particular, the way they see the extrinsic world. Of course, the energy it takes to keep this truth hidden from oneself is much greater than the energy it takes to hide it from one's peers, because

someone with a broad capacity for interpretation can deduce what is going on with the tattoo user and even determine his character, without this affecting his own life.

What should be taken care of is in relation to those who presume to know how to carry out this type of semiotic analysis, because it is not about interpreting a painting, in which some artist has left his mark there, expressing his world, his age, his endocrine complexities - biological, reflected on their affectivity. The tattoo becomes something of high complexity because it represents the most authentic totality of the being itself, what in fact it is, its explicit identity.

When someone gets a tattoo with the intention of honoring someone, a friend, a family member, a pet, this only confirms that he has not overcome his physical loss and, thus, through a substitute, he tries to make up for his absence, placing him in your body and in such a way that it will never leave it [*or that it can be left by it*]. It is a pathological case, difficult to interpret and even to define the type of conscious and unconscious affective bond that united them. It may even be sending a message to the deceased, in the afterlife, that now he will no longer be able to leave him alone in this world that does not understand his pain.

What is known as a fact is that the individual who gets tattoos on his body suffers from egodystonics and the drawing on display is a way of seeking some kind of psychological balance that, as it undergoes changes, whether for the better or worse, other drawings are represented until you have an [*apparently*] unintelligible mosaic.

The Government of England, under the reign of George V (1865-1936), adopted the tattoo as a way of identifying criminals, in 1879; from then on, the tattoo gained an outlaw connotation in the West. Still in the 19th century, it was common, in Europe and America, for tattooed men and women to be presented as a circus attraction. It was something, considered, as extremely exotic. The influence of Christian ideology was what most led to the condition that marginalized individuals and in moral conflict with society used drawings on their skin. This leads to the interpretation that, in addition to the unconscious feeling that there is an internal conflict in which the desire to be the figure represented on the body weighs, there is a conscious conflict in which a direct affront to a symbol of order can be demonstrated. social or an attempt to show everyone that it embodies the same values as the sign represented on its body.

In any case, what we have is an exposed conflict, for which the individual does not know a solution. His intention with the exhibition of the drawing is to cause consternation, to draw attention and, if someone interpolates him on the figure, his answer is *always* harsh and rude, claiming that the other is prejudiced and, each time this happens, it only reinforces his belief

that he lives in a backward world, full of intellectually backward people. Nowadays, the tattoo will always express the existence and representation of an egodystonic person.

This particular condition ends up revealing other traits of society and individual behavior, where one perceives the loss of music quality, distancing from politics, the end of the conflict represented by love and hate in an ambivalent relationship directed at the same object and, once more Nietzsche's argument (2006), as a revelation, is that all the energy that is not put out turns against the being itself and, once this happens, there is an enraged animal struggling and scratching the walls of his cage, injuring himself to exhaustion or even death.

Roughly speaking, society in general harbors the naive idea that by placing any drawing on the body, the individual incorporates everything that that character represents within the generalized semantic universe; eg, when tattooing an image of the Joker, one becomes sadistic, violent, crazy, assuming bizarre and sociopathic, even psychopathic, attitudes. It turns out that, it is completely the opposite of this; when implanting a tattoo, the previous choice is for an image that can express everything that has been stored in thought, including even the epigenetic variations resulting from intra and interpersonal confrontations caused by particular choices [good or bad] and elapsed from the existential *experience* of each individual.

More and more people are seeing individuals covering parts of their bodies with tattoos and, when analyzing, in an accurate way, the images used, what is noticed is that the variety of drawings is minimal, with the same symbols persisting for an ever-increasing range. of users. It is not that they have the same internalized feeling or the same repressed desire; the situation posed is that they feel in the possibility of expressing as they understand what is trapped and, if you try to talk to each one, you will have a great surprise as to what they reveal about the painting exposed on their bodies.

They never say what the drawing really means, precisely because a much more powerful entity forbids them to do so; at most, allowing them to expose their conflicts and letting others analyze them and issue their value judgments. For those who believe that there is no type of conflict going on in the individual's intrinsic world, the revelations of its exposed forms demonstrate the opposite. Of course, an interpretation as close as possible to the personological reality will demand much more than mere knowledge about the semantic meaning of the drawings, which, roughly speaking, are nothing more than figures represented on someone's skin. Thus, it is necessary to look into the individual's life history so that the deductions lead to an understanding of what is happening in their affective field.

pathos is and will always be an enigma to be deciphered and this condition can only be achieved through deduction, because any human *being* feels very bad about having their secrets

violated by anyone. Every tattooed individual wants others to look at their designs from an aesthetic point of view; never investigative and deductive. The conscious explanation they give for each drawing, as if it represented, summarizing, by itself and in itself, the whole story of a life, in a certain way, becomes enchanting.

By referring here to *pathos*, he has it as a deep feeling, something that crosses the whole being and links it to the sublime and, contrary to what one might believe, conflict is an integral part of the human personological conjuncture, in which its presence [*explicit or not*] does not diminish or increase the individual value of each being. There are symbols that, on very rare occasions, will be seen tattooed on someone's body, and this is because of the symbolic force they contain, in itself. This already demonstrates that man applies to his body representations that he can withstand and that he believes he can dominate when necessary.

This inheritance of connection with the totemic animal is a phylogenetic anthropological phenomenon, in which all the inhabitants of the tribe had this voluptuous feeling of keeping within themselves the spirit of the protective animal and becoming invincible and immortal, like the heroes of the told legends. Even though the world has developed in such a way as to bury primitive beliefs and all their miraculous power, the changes have not been enough to destroy this longing for a time not experienced by human beings today. In this regard, when an individual in phenomenological conflict with himself makes the decision to get a tattoo, he feels indecisive until he is confronted with the animal that represents his emotional state characterized as egodystonic, his amorphous *pathos*. Later, one hears from him that it was like something magical, in which one only had to look at the drawing in the catalog that one felt as if one were being called by him to merge into one body and spirit.

This adolescent projection link represents one of the strongest reasons why some people regret getting tattoos on their bodies. It happens that an egodystonic person can become an egosyntonic person and, once the conflict is over, what is the meaning of the conflicting representation to remind him of what was once something that he did not know how to live in harmony with and, he does not even know the reason why I was always fighting with him... In the same way as the scourges that transform a being into someone at war with himself, loves come and go, creating voids that cannot be filled by drawings on the skin. The arrival of love brings joy and its departure is, almost always, a paradox, which is divided between the pleasure of freedom and the sadness of absence, always marking new forms of expression and worldview.

Those who try to see their aesthetic productions on their own bodies as an act of freedom are deceiving themselves by letting their fragile ego expose their pain or happiness to anyone

who is willing to admire it, or not. For decades, tattoos were the subject of heavy rock groups, beings in conflict with themselves and also with society, and what may sound strange is that society itself allowed them to exist, because they served as a magical attribute for teenagers. As they crossed the *stage of the mirror*, with which they could deceive and fantasize, looking towards them and their excesses, their peaceful and boring lives.

Tattoos, as already mentioned above, are very old expressions due to the totemic ritual and beliefs in supernatural powers that originated from tales and that, little by little, were being internalized in such a way in tribal life that it was transformed into absolute truths. As soon as,

Tattooing is an ancient practice, which was developed by people all over the world in different periods of history. The modern tattoo procedure is carried out with an electric machine, to which a needle is attached that penetrates superficially into the skin, taking with it the pigment that will definitively mark the design on its living support. Despite the relative pain caused by the procedure, *tattooing* is an object of desire for a large part of the population, of all ages. The practice has already been used for various purposes, from a form of expression to marking prisoners, reaching the level of publicity and diffusion obtained from the end of the 20th century. Permeated with prejudice due to its shady uses in different parts of the world, the practice has been gradually gaining acceptance (GONÇALVES, 2017, p. 12-13).

There is no way to say that certain people used the procedures of tattooing their bodies more than others; but the sacred detail behind the technique is what makes such an action a recurrent practice among different peoples, even if the geographical conditions do not even allow one to imagine that one day they had any kind of contact. This leads to think of the hypothesis that something in common connects all humans, which could be a condition of fear, satisfaction, passion, the sacred or faith itself, which before being, was simply beliefs in things that went beyond their comprehension.

It was not difficult for man with the already evolved capacity for abstraction to come to the understanding that by applying the image of the animal on his own body he would take all his strength and capabilities superior [to his] for survival in the wild *world*. In this way, it is not difficult to believe that the execution of images on the body was not a deliberate decision by anyone who so wished. There was a whole rite of passage to which the candidate to be tattooed would have to undergo, in order to verify that he was, in fact, the one chosen by the animal that would be engraved on his skin, because once the process was carried out, there was no way return to the previous state; he would come to hold the strength and physical capacity and cunning of that specimen designed in him.

In the context of changes in thinking and, consequently, with the loosening of the rites of passage, the way found to prevent people from getting tattooed without any criteria, trapped in the superstition that a community of beastmen should be formed, the transmutation of sacred prohibition became a prejudice, which led many not to adopt it as a style of body adornment. As superstitions were falling away, institutions, in particular those that remained most closely linked to tradition, created explicit rules that prevented those who had a tattoo on their bodies from effectively entering their bodies. This caused the practice to be kept on the sidelines for many years.

In recent years, due to the softening of customs and loss of tradition, many people have carried out the experience of creating a tattoo on their bodies, displaying them as if they were trophies to a society that watches all this plunged in the deepest silence. In this sense, one cannot simply say that there is a *progressive acceptance* of tattoos by society; it is tradition and rites that are losing all their historical function and power that made possible the construction of the moral pillars of human life, with all its phylogenetic processes.

What can never be lost sight of is that the element with greater power must be the one who decides on the one with lesser power, that is, society must be the one who determines the course of individual life and, if this is not obeyed, there is an existence marked by a consequent symbolic violence applied against himself by the individual himself. While the social order, supported by a tradition in which this, in turn, remains alive as a reminder of the rule of law. Getting tattoos cannot be the product of a frivolous and childish decision. If the art of tattooing consisted of simply placing any design on the skin and applying an aesthetic aspect to it, there would be no reason to promote any kind of discussion and analysis. From the walls of the caves, the animals represented in them passed to the surface of the body of the warriors and this was the result of a long period of observation and beliefs based on empirical events.

Following this same principle of belief,

The tattoo has already been used as a form of spiritual protection by different peoples, even by Catholics at different times. Despite the prohibition by Pope Hadrian I (700-795), in 787, Roman soldiers tattooed [*images of*] crosses on their chests during the Crusades, in order to have a Christian burial if they died in combat. Between the 15th and 17th centuries, during the Turkish-Ottoman invasion of Bosnia and Herzegovina, Catholics tattooed crosses in order not to be forced to pray to Allah (BELLO, 2017, p. 35).

What is clear was the search for protection against enemy weapons. It was very common to feed the belief that with the use of some symbols, considered sacred, the body became invulnerable. Therefore, the use of tattoos using images of elements consecrated by Christianity

was not considered as a contravention of the papal decree, because everything was for the cause in the name of God. One cannot abandon the hypothesis that such designs were imposed on soldiers who went to this war already knowing what would happen to them if they were captured and the implantation of tattoos on their bodies was a superior order.

The use of symbols as instruments of protection is a practice that is lost in the sands of human history, recorded from the paintings of animals on the walls of caves to the use of amulets, passing through the insertion of these same symbols in the body itself. No matter what time you are living, man is a being who is taken by superstition and uses it to move forward in a voracious, unknown world with forces far superior to his own. The fear of being surprised by some evil is what makes them seek, for themselves, certain types of protection through faith, based on beliefs and superstitions, the most varied.

Even today, humans keep these primitive feelings and it is very common to see tattoos of rosaries, saints, religious symbols on the body and even saints. Blind and immoderate devotion awakens archaic feelings that are not in line with the times we live in, [*apparently*] more enlightened and, ideologically, more grounded in the sciences and from and on empirical precepts.

Within a context of anthropological analysis, man is dependent on symbols that enable him to have some kind of protection against various evils against which he does not find ways to feel safe, because he believes in these idiosyncrasies that were being created by his developed brain and potentially creative. It is permissible for him to carry such magical paraphernalia; but, inserting them into your body is something that goes beyond the simple precept of guarding the symbolic object. With the weakening of customs and religion itself, this has become an object of individual decision with which society cannot interfere, despite its role as curator and guardian of tradition.

CASES STUDIES

In order to illustrate this article, 2 (two) *cases will be presented* , in which individual tattoo users used them as literal expressions of their deepest feelings; one, in relation to a lost love and the other, in relation to his particular way of looking at life and his human existence, in the world he chose for himself. These situations will be analyzed in detail.

The first case refers to a woman who separated from her partner, with whom she had had a marital relationship for many years. As soon as they got together, she had her husband's name tattooed on her forearm and, so it remained until the end of the relationship when she

went to a tattoo studio and ordered them to make an image of a feather over her ex-husband's name. When asked the reason for drawing a feather on his arm, he couldn't answer objectively, just saying that that image was what first came to his mind when he was choosing a drawing to cover the old tattoo.

What happens is that this was the feeling I felt for my ex-husband: Pity, mercy; in popular jargon, *pity*; that is to say, he considered his ex-consort as someone who, without his help, would be condemned to misery. However, the tattoo not only expresses what she feels about the boy, but also her individual character, in which she exalts herself by demoting the other to a miserable and emotionally dependent condition. All that his tattoo demonstrates is the very condition of denial of his weakness in the face of the abandonment of his beloved, the consternation that was transmuted into hatred, aversion to the individual. Perhaps not even she knows what she really feels for the boy, and the choice of a drawing representing a feather to cover up his name is an unmeasured, thoughtless act, practiced during a moment when she needed to vent her anger against the fact of having been rejected by him.

It must always be very clear that a drawing stamped on the body does not reflect the individual's life story, because this is volatile and transmutes over time, according to various situations [good and bad] that affect him during his years of existence. . What this stigma points to is the existence of a conflict that occurred and that caused an epigenetic mutation in the being, which does not mean, under any circumstances, that he has become another being, another creature, completely lost all his previous psychological characteristics.

Even if another drawing is superimposed over the original drawing, containing and presenting a new semantic expression, the first one does not cease to exist, much less the cause, the pathos that led it to be built, in the same way as its primordial phylogenetic semantic *characteristic* .

Many people believe that once drawing has been superseded, everything it represented and expressed is superseded. Once again, we reiterate what Nietzsche said: *What do you want to hide?* And, the most interesting thing was the rhetorical juggling that the woman in the aforementioned *case* used to hide her ambiguous feelings towards her ex-consort. Even because in the Judeo-Christian culture, feeling pity or pity, mercy for someone is a feeling that reveals an affective cathexis in relation to the object.

As Nietzsche makes clear, everything that human beings create is not just an expression of themselves; or, as he used to say and ended up becoming a social convention, that expressed creativity is a way of showing what you feel to the other. Quite the contrary; it is an opportunity to keep hidden what, in fact, it brings with it and that is causing situations of endogenous

conflicts. Tattoos reveal this, in a very striking way and with an intense empirical character. Even if an interpretive paradox can occur, in which what is taken as a deciphered enigma may not be in line with the empirical reality, within the semantic scope there is not the slightest possibility of failure, regarding the understanding of the thing itself, which reveals all the conflict faced during a certain moment of life.

The second that will be reported here is, by its very nature, complex and proved to be very challenging due to the fact that it represented 3 (three) phases of the individual's life and, at first sight, an animal was placed in front of us that was not part of our semantic-mnemonic universe, that is, it was completely unknown, until it was deciphered and discovered that it was 3 (three) images, one superimposed on the other.

The individual in question was an ex-convict who had just served his sentence for bank robbery. This was his specialty since he was young, used to heavy and high-risk situations. However, he had a superior talent, which was the ability to camouflage and disguise himself, a condition that, according to him, on several occasions, had saved him from being captured during police sieges. For this reason he tattooed an animal on his foot, a salamander, which does not match his artistic ability; but we deduced that it was a misinterpretation by the tattoo artist who confused a chameleon with the mythological animal that resists fire. And, ironically, due to his technique for using disguises and managing to blend in with the people and go unnoticed, he was nicknamed Chameleon by his fellow adventurers .

As he got older, his attacks on bank robberies became more aggressive and violent, and this messed with the boy's mind, in which, realizing the situation was getting worse and the possibility of death at any moment, this provoked different feelings in his mind. state of being, which led him to treat life based on *all or nothing*. Believing this to be his free nature, he tattooed a scorpion over the old salamander tattoo.

This animal means anything goes and there is even a legend that illustrates well this special condition of being: A scorpion asks a frog to take him across a river. The frog is afraid of being stung during the trip, but the scorpion argues that if it stings the frog, the frog would sink and the scorpion would drown. The frog agrees and starts to carry the scorpion, but, in the middle of the way, the scorpion ends up stinging the frog, condemning both to death. When asked by the frog why it had stung him, the scorpion replies that this is its nature and that nothing could be done to change fate.

But behold, a beautiful lady appears to change the boy's destiny. Amidst the lull between one robbery and another, he meets a girl, with whom he falls in love and they even get married. From this union comes a daughter and life goes on very normally, with him getting a good job

and fulfilling himself as a husband, father and a domestic life. His whole thought changes and existential continuity becomes more important than anything else in his life and, as a result, he tattoos an Egyptian cross on the ancient image, which symbolically refers to life as an absolute value, being above all else.

What is observed in this *case* and that can be interpreted is that each drawing was chosen by the individual to symbolize what was happening in his state of being; they weren't random choices and tattoos made in moments of euphoria or in a state of ecstasy caused by alcohol. He was, apparently, a simple, calm, polite boy who, by his behavior, would never point to the deduction that he hid such a complex and violent life trajectory.

As discussed elsewhere, the traditional symbology of the elements available to tattoo artists and all the aesthetics they apply to the drawings, transforming them into brilliant pieces of art, does not eliminate the contextualized semantics they assume, in each case, in particular, in that object choice is the result of an intrinsic latent desire to expose the conflict that the individual is unable to bear.

Each stage of his life revealed, through the designs tattooed on his body, does not mean that the next one has destroyed or supplanted the predecessors. Many actions lose their meaning as time goes by and the age that caused that situation to have a certain meaning ceases to make any emotional sense. This is what happened to the individual exposed in the aforementioned *case*. The heavy game in the criminal world, especially for bank robbers, is not killing people, nor is it physically injuring them; what matters is to awaken terror and fear and feed on the situation of dread that grips everyone, seeing the fear expressed on their faces. Ironically, it is very rare to find members of these groups using any type of tattoo. This was a special case that came to us as a finding, which is now being explored in this essay-article.

CONCLUSION

The use of tattoos (drawings) on part of the body is a technique that possibly originated from religious beliefs and superstitions and, little by little, took on spaces of marginalization, as religion and its set of miraculous protections were losing their magical effect on individuals.

What stands out in this essay-article is that each drawing, in particular, has a unique semantic structure and the way it is expressed on the body is what will determine its symbology, portraying the conflict and its dimension in individual thought. For example, rose means love in at least 12 (twelve) languages, because the English word *rose* is nothing more than an anagram of Eros, the god of love, in Greek mythology. However, the way it is represented in

the drawing will determine the expression and quantum of this feeling in the individual, and may even express aversion to affective love towards the other person.

Butterflies mean freedom; however, its position will tell if the individual wants to be free alone, fly through the air disconnected from the world or if he is open to receiving the values and goods that others may be interested in offering him. Tattooing sacred symbols on the body is a way to seek protection against curses, plagues, punishments, envy of others.

In the distant past, tattooing images of animals on the body meant incorporating the brute, savage strength and power of such beings into oneself, making one capable of defeating opponents in battles and hunting. In contemporary times, these images say what goes on in the thoughts of such people and express their state of character and personological state. For example, whoever tattoos a scorpion is the type of individual that, for him, nothing matters, being willing to do anything to follow his path. Whoever tattoos snakes on his body is an individual who inspires little confidence, dangerous, treacherous.

A little used symbol in tattoos is the horse, exactly because the symbolism of this animal is very strong, expressing the father figure and also the wild and indomitable fury of nature, which can never be controlled. From Plato (428/427-348/347 ane), with his legend of the black knight, to Arthur Schopenhauer (1788-1860), dealing with the same theme, and Sigmund Freud (1856-1939), who uses the same metaphor to say that the man mounted on the horse believes that he dominates it, in which this belief is an illusion based on the condition that the horse does not rebel, remains docile and obedient.

Each drawing has its symbology and a very particular semantic character, and the context in which they are found is decisive for the meaning they express. Even religious symbols and saints, such as the image of Our Lady of Aparecida and Jesus Christ, should be analyzed more rigorously, as they can express unpleasant situations experienced by their users.

The study of tattoos is very specific and, even if one has mastery over semiotics, semantics and interpretation of drawings, this is still not enough to interpret the meaning of the image when displayed on a given individual. Only his particular life story can open the way to a broad and profound interpretation of the symbolic meaning of the art expressed in his body, because under no circumstances will his egodytonic expose what actually happens in his body. their inner world, in terms of conflict and violence. The individual will consciously sublimate any possible reading of his state of being.

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